

Mechanical Properties on Natural Fiber Hybrid Composites

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Abstract:- Researchers, engineers, and scientists have recently become interest in naturally available filaments due to their suitability as a respond in a way for fiber reinforced composites. Low cost, good mechanical qualities, non-abrasive, and biodegradable features, utilized as a substitute for conventional fibred. The interfacial bond between material and the fibers is what determines the tractable characteristics of typical fiber reinforced composites. The effects of fiber length, chemical treatments of long areca fibers, and the influence of Maceration just on strength properties of shorter and longer areca fibers, but also areca husk, are all discussed in this article.

Keywords:- Natural composites Fiber; reinforced composites; Areca nut fiber; Mechanical properties; Chemical treatment.

I. INTRODUCTION

The world today is faced with the tough aim of building new advanced inventions and methods to dispose of or utilize waste materials, particularly non-reversible polymers[1]. The techniques for breaking down these wastes are inept and will result in the related to hazardous substances. Given the given characteristics, the only approach to get a solution would be to strengthen polymers with natural fabrics. Normal strands are a decreased, reusable, and eco-accommodating materials. There the pliable properties are astounding, and they might be utilized. to supplanting strands like as More grounded mixes with glass and carbon [2]. A key disadvantage of using remarkable layers as invigorating in saps is that they make unfortunate association between ordinary shafts and frameworks polymers, because of low flexible characteristics [3]. To further develop filaments interface restricting and crossover inconstancy, certain thoughts and surfaces modifying techniques have without a doubt been investigated. Besides, filaments over-burdening fundamentally affects the design and unbending nature of bio composites polymer composites [4]. Raising the fiber weight dissemination works on mechanical properties up to a certain extent. Components of numerical conditions are a helpful device for assessing the tractable properties of regular fiber.[5] Cellulose strands is made out of various parts, including cellulose, lignin, and celluloses. as either an aftereffect of lignin, gelatin, and different parts normal proof of the presence of specific part The characteristics of fiber are extraordinary. Higher water contents, yet affects Framework fiber attaching To fix the issue, Pharmacological elective medicines have been an obstacle. as per the plan

and broke down accomplish highlights that are practically identical with those of other [6] person strands In ongoing composites events, what's more, an assortment of purposes, including power Glass fiber built up protection made of areca/betel nut Polymers enjoy a ton of benefits. The not entirely settled by the fiber properties. albeit the versatile strength is a lot higher lattice qualities delicate [7]. Areca/betel nuts composite materials having acquired extraordinary advantages in late materials happenings and pertinence, including cover system [8]. This not set in stone by fiber properties, while the yield point is significantly more receptive to frameworks properties.

II. CLASSIFICATION OF NATURAL FIBERS

Normal threads would be any unpolished tresses material that can be applied to a variety of places, including plants, animals, and metals. Furthermore, such unpolished constituents are then switched to weave patterns, and then that they may be made into fibers, thread, etc. or, but at another paw, wire, which is then used as part of Polymer combinations Gadgets can also be put to use. [7] To manufacture papers there's a whole lot of them. Natural hairs with regular patterns and many Researchers have given their opinion on It employ standard fibers and typical threads. Encourage its use of regular monofilament and make an effort to improve on fiberglass characteristics with the help of ordinary strands A clustering of normal filaments is seen in Figure. Plants, creatures, and rocks all include normal threads. Typical threads can all be classified and segregated into organism threads, vegetation lignin fibrils, but also nutrient cords, as specified by chemical, properties.

Fig. 1: Types of Natural Fiber

III. ADVANTAGES OF NATURAL FIBER COMPOSITES

A. High strength

In the structure business, materials like lightweight materials are utilized on the grounds that they have incredible fortitude in all ways. Elastomers might be made to in any case be profoundly strong composites, yet they would be developed with a specific goal in mind.

B. Sturdy

Composites have a full life yet rather consistently need overhauling when used to develop a development. Numerous composites have 50 years life expectancy. Be that as it may, we may not realize how long a fiber built up development might be shown to be sturdy, nor do we know where early composite materials will be old.

C. Warm conductivity is low

Protection is given by regular fiber. The individuals who safeguard structures again from components by being used for windows, window casings, and braces. Despite the facts that bioplastics struggle with communicating chill or warm.

D. The connection among strength and high

The sturdiness connection is a lattice composites highlight that gives us informant and furthermore provides us with a sign of how intense, weighty, or softness it is. Nan composites are powerful, yet they are likewise light. Thus, engineered filaments might be utilized in both airplane industry and auto design [9].

E. Light weight

Fiberglass is employed in aeronautical but also industrial development because they are small and light. Hybrid composites are less dense with conventional timber and aluminum. Synthetic fibers are being employed in the construction of recent aero planes but since people are obsessed over fuel economy, which can be achieved by using lighter bio composites. Specific mechanical and oxidation resistance.

F. Corrosion resistance and high-impact strength

Characteristics of opposition and high energy ingestion limit It can recuperate anyplace and get through barometrical mischief. Dependability is phenomenal in example. It tends to be serious in any encompassing or meteorological condition [4]. Elastomers are as yet used to deliver bombproof coats and boards, as well as to safeguard planes, lodging improvements, and military trucks with bombings, because of their capacity to retain any surprising power.

G. Dimensional stability

Biomaterials are in such a state of stability. Rain and temperatures have little effect on their form or size. When the temperature changes, though, pine bends and blooms. As a result, materials have desired system to fit in every condition, which is why they are used to construct helicopter wing tips so that their form and dimensions do not vary in any conditions, whether hot or cold.

H. Nonconductive

Nonconductive nature of a combination This implies that cross breeds can't ionize. Heterogeneous materials are considered to make electrical organization posts and wiring over this component. Whenever permittivity is expected in nanocomposites, changing their characteristics into copper is extremely straightforward.

I. Nonmagnetic

Nanocomposites are noncorrosive, that is the sole component they is being utilized in abodes and tables, as well as encompassing electrical things and as a supported material in the development of substantial drywall in medical clinics.

J. Radar transparent

Radar frameworks are made of blends, and carbon filaments texture is used in shitlist to communicate signals on the light falling. Polymers are used to make airplane like the US Flying corps' B-2 top secret plane, which is utilized to communicate.

IV. TENSILE STRENGTH

On sisal composite materials and nanocomposite with various characteristics, the impact of various chemical treatments based on classifications have been studied. Banana peels treated with NaOH. In this study, banana fibers were used to compare the tensile characteristics of untreated and chemically modified banana fibre reinforced composites [2]. In general, stiffness is preferred above important structural component by the majority of common strands. The stiffness of banana strands was examined in

this study, and a comparative was conducted with the 96 several well characteristic filaments. When compared to untreated fiber, P.chrysosporium showed a 35.1 percentage increase in quality while Obtain a clearer sp. showed a 25.7 percent increase in quality. Lignin is the component that makes the fibre weak. Total abolition of lignin enables various sections of the filaments, such as cellulose, to become considerably more conservative, increasing the performance and flexibility of a areca husk fibre[4].

Fig. 2: Ultimate tensile strength of areca fibers reinforced epoxy composite

After being alkalinized inside a 1 percent NaOH solution the solution hour, the mechanical properties of sisal fibers were investigated. These alkalinized fibres had a great specific strength of BFRPC with a fibre loading of 10 to 30%, but with a fiber content of 113 to 40%, the tensile modulus declined (Fig. 1). Some experiments employed soluble base treated strands with excellent elasticity qualities, as well as KOH (Potassium Permanganate) treatment filament in composites, which demonstrated better ductility (Fig. 2) than untouched filament composites. The breakage strength

of long betel quid and areca filaments was examined using various treatment media. The pH was measured, but different surface treatment medium including such jaggery and wheat flour solution were used [15]. To evaluate the stiffness of banana fibres, tests were done on treated and untreated filaments. Fibers treated with salt solution exhibited 34 percent higher strength than untreated fibres, while treatment with jaggery solutions enhanced the strength by 31 percent [8].

Fig. 3: Stress–strain curves of untreated and treated unripe, ripe and matured BNH fibers.

V. OTHER CHEMICAL TREATMENTS

The effect of various chemical treatments on the tensile behaviour of banana and pineapple fibres is discussed in this section. ASTM standard methodologies have been adopted for the testing of the stiffness of untreated as well as all artificially prepared banana fibre supplemented regular elastic composites [12]. The elasticity of unprocessed and all semi - synthetic treated fibres supplemented typical elastic composites was shown as expanded with an increase in fibre stacking of up to 60%, followed by a reduction [17]. Epoxy

acridity covered banana carbon strands basic erosion coefficient materials with 60% fiber stacking had the biggest solidness of both the uncoated and covered pineapple fibres routine strength blends. In fact, functionalization of filaments (1 N sodium alginate elective [Na₂CO₃]) upgrade the strength of areca carp covers biobased cements, however that was found that fiber surface alteration can work on the limiting in both engineered strands (influence strength of 38.96 N) [16].

Fig. 4: Stress–strain curves of raw, ripe and matured BNH fibers.

VI. FIBER MATURITY

To see how cashew nut measurements affect structural stress, we examined the tensile modulus of betel nut shell (BNH) fibers at three stages of development (raw, flowering, and finished). Fruit BNH has high strength and is an attractive material as a polymer fiber material [5]. Dried BNH fibers are less dense than aged BNH fibers due to lower moisture levels, but the surface strength of the dried BNH fibers is better. In additional studies, in terms of the mechanical properties of strength, mature BNH fibers have maximum strength (166.03 MPa), followed by mature BNH fibers (128.79 MPa) and raw BNH fibers (123.92 MPa). I understand (Fig. 4). The tensile strength of BNH fiber was compared with the tensile strength of kenaf fiber strength properties (129–473 MPa) [16].

VII. HYBRID COMPOSITES

Hybrid synthesis is created by fusing 2 or more fibers into a unified form and is often abbreviated as "hybrid". This section [18] examined the interaction of two fibers (managed pineapple and others). Tensile tests of chemical bananas, jute fiber copolymers and undiagnosed fiber biomaterials were compared, and it was found that the impregnated fibers performed better than the non-sensitized fibers. Figure 7 [18] shows progressive overburden in fibers

treated with 10% NaOH. Laminate of epoxy and rambutan fiber The tensile strength (compressive strength, flexural strength and effect) of polyester carbon fiber (PP) loaded with narrow betel nut (Bn) fiber at different percentages (3, 5, 10, 20 and 30 wt%) always show decreasing mechanical properties as the filler ratio expands, and the fibers exhibit reduced warping qualities as the mixture ratio increases % of the filler, and composites with 10% pineapple fiber exhibited the better mechanical properties [14].

The quality of the hybrid nanocomposites will be improved by combining hemp fabric and a small amount of Sansevieria with Matrix alloys according to the ideal ratio (Bn10:Sc10: PP:80) of the fiber surface texture [15]. Carbon compounds are used as building materials in a wide variety of products where hardness and cost are important factors to consider. The flexible modulus of composition 300B (700g banana fiber + 300g sisal powder + 300cc phenol formaldehyde) was tested, which is the strongest of all the performances in one data. A bio combination of bio-ethylene and unprocessed raw banana peel jute (UNASFRPM) was tested for its tensile properties [12]. Experiments and Finite Element Analysis (FEA) were performed on a UNASFRPM 260 hash, and the results (16.16 N/mm² and 19.6473 N/mm² for experimental and FEA results, respectively) close to 262 adjacent reports [17].

VIII. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Tensile properties

For compared to known fibres such as sisal, bamboo, coir, and banana, the thickness of the vakka fibre was just very low, which was an appealing criterion when constructing lightweight materials. The diameters of the various fibres studied ranged from 175 to 250 micro meter. The ultimate tensile and stiffness of vakka fiber-reinforced composites are discussed, as well as sisal, bamboo, and banana composites.

In contrast to sisal, bamboo, and banana composites, the influence of volume percent of fibre on strength and modulus for vakka fiber-reinforced composites. The ultimate tensile of all fiber-reinforced composites studied in this work increases as the volume fraction of fibre increases, in the sequence of sisal, banana, vakka, and jute bamboo. The tensile modulus of vakka fibre composite is roughly 32 percent greater than that of sisal and banana composite, respectively, and comparable to that of bamboo composite at a volume fraction of fibre 0.37 in the composite. When compared to sisal and banana, this improvement is due to the strength and better bonding of vakka fibre with the polyester matrix.

In the sequence of banana, sisal, vakka, and bamboo, the elastic strength of all composite studied in the this study increases with the volume proportion of fibre in the composite.

B. Methodology

To eliminate common and recurring errors, this technique goes through many steps of an injection molding process [5]. The procedures listed so far are very important in test preparation for test results [8].

- The fibers are collected and prepared.
- Mass percent at a given conversion.
- Prepare the mold.
- These fibers are cut to a size of 0.5 mm.
- Order of data storage.
- Preparing to melt plastic
- The epoxy is removed from the mold.
- Excavating and finishing samples Cut and reduce diameter according to ASTM standards.

C. Raw Materials:

- Raw materials used in this experimental Works are:
- Natural fibers Banana and pineapple
- Epoxy resin
- Hardener.

IX. CONCLUSIONS

The results indicate that when the weight percentage of natural fibre in epoxy composites, the wear resistance falls. The water absorption rate steadily rose with increasing banana fibre loading in a 7-day water absorption test, with the minimum moisture content attained with % sisal fibre and % banana fibre loading [17]. The use of pineapple fibre in composite materials provides a new supply of materials that are cost-effective, environmentally benign, and

recyclable. The hybrid composites produced by combining natural and synthetic fibres have increased mechanical strength and may be used in tribological applications with greater loading. Weight loss, friction coefficient, wear, and friction coefficient are all reduced in composite samples 30B-70P Due to appropriate bonding among matrix and the reinforcement, displays decreased weight loss, frictional force, wear, and coefficient of friction with varying loads at 1m/s slide velocity when compared to the pure composite and other hybrid composites [13]. In M 20 concrete grade, the addition of 0.5 percent, 60 per cent, and 1.5 percent fibres increases the tensile strength by 6.5 per cent, 2.09 percent, and 0.54 %, respectively [5].

REFERENCES

- [1.] ASTM G99-17, Standard Test method for Wear Testing with a Pinon-Disk Apparatus, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2017, www.astm.org.
- [2.] K. G. Satyanarayana, K.Sukumaran, P. S. Mukherjee, C.Pavithran, S.G.K. Pillai, "Natural fibre-polymer composites," Cement and Concrete Composites, vol. 12, pp. 117- 136, 1990.
- [3.] Olga Mysiukiewicz, Tomasz Sterzynski, "Influence of water on Tribological Properties of Wood-Polymer Composites," Archives of Mechanical Technology and materials. vol. 37, pp. 79-84, 2017.
- [4.] M.H.P.S. Jawaid& H. A. Khalil, "Cellulosic/synthetic reinforced polymer hybrid composites: A review," Carbohydrate Polymers, 86(1), 1-18, 2011.
- [5.] Ebisike K, AttahDaniel B. E, Babatope B, Olusunle S. O, "Studies on the extraction of Naturally-Occurring Banana Fibers," International Journal of Engineering and Science, Vol. 2, Issue 9, pp. 95-99, 2013.
- [6.] Fairuz FazillahShuhimi, MohdFadzli Bin Abdollah, Md Abul kalam, Masjuki Hassan, Ashafie Mustafa, HilmiAmiruddin, "Tribological Characteristics comparison for oil palm fibre/epoxy and kenaf fibre/epoxy composites under dry sliding conditions," Tribology International, Vol. 101, pp. 247- 254, Sept. 2016.
- [7.] Umar Nirmala. N, Jamil Hashima, M. M. H. Megat Ahmad, "A review on tribological performance of natural fibre polymeric composites," Tribology international, Vol. 83, pp. 77-104, 2015.
- [8.] Sudhankar Majhi, S.P.Samantarai, S.K.Acharya, "Tribological Behavior of Modified Rice husk filled epoxy composite," International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research, Vol. 3, Issue 6, June2012.
- [9.] U. Nirmal, J. Hashim and S.T.W. Lau, "Testing Methods in tribology of polymeric composites," International Journal of Mechanical and Mechatronics Engineering, Vol. 6, pp. 367-373, 2011.
- [10.] Abhishek kumar Choubey, Suraj Mukti, "Tribological Characterization of Natural Fiber Composites," International Journal of Engineering Science and Computing, Vol. 7, Issue No. 7, 2017.
- [11.] K. Karthik, P. Senthilkumar, "Tribological Characteristics of CarbonEpoxy with ceramic particles composites for centrifugal pump bearing Application,"

- International Journal of ChemTech Research, Vol.8, No. 6, pp. 612-620, 2015.
- [12.] Sivakumar. M, Ranjith Kumar. M, "Mechanical properties and SEM analysis of glass/nylon/jute reinforced epoxy hybrid composites," International Journal of Mechanical and Mechatronics Engineering, Vol. 7, pp. 196-207, MarchApril 2016.
- [13.] Dr A Thimmana Gouda, Jagadish S P, Dr K R Dinesh, Virupaksha Gouda H, Dr N Prashanth, "Wear Study on Hybrid Natural Fiber Polymer Composite Materials Used As Orthopaedic Implants," International Journal of Recent Development in Engineering and Technology , Vol. 3, Issue 1, July 2014.
- [14.] M. Maleque, F. Belal, and S. Sapuan, "Mechanical properties study of pseudostem banana fiber reinforced epoxy composite," The Arabian journal for science and engineering, vol. 32, pp. 359- 364, 2007.
- [15.] H. Ismail, M. Edyham, and B. Wirjosentono, "Bamboo fibre filled natural rubber composites: the effects of filler loading and bonding agent," Polymer testing, vol. 21, pp. 139-144, 2002.
- [16.] H. Sastra, J. Siregar, S. Sapuan, Z. Leman, and M. Hamdan, "Flexural properties of Arenga Pinnata fibre reinforced epoxy composites," American Journal of Applied Sciences, pp. 21-24, 2005.
- [17.] C. Chin and B. Yousif, "Potential of kenaf fibres as reinforcement for tribological applications," Wear, vol. 267, pp. 1550-1557, 2009. [18] U. Nirmal, B. Yousif, D. Rilling, and P. Brevern, "Effect of betelnut fibres treatment and contact conditions on adhesive wear and frictional performance of polyester composites," Wear, vol. 268, pp. 1354-1370, 2010.